

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH IN RELATION TO EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Dr Vanika Nagpal

Principal, Jiwan Jyoti College, Jalalabad (W), Fazilka (Punjab)

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Received: **01/08/2025**

Accepted: **20/09/2025**

Published: **30/09/2025**

Keywords:

Academic Achievement, English, Emotional Intelligence, Secondary School Students, Gender

ABSTRACT

This study examined academic achievement in English in relation to emotional intelligence among secondary school students. Recognizing English as a compulsory and globally significant subject, the study focused on the extent to which students' emotional competencies are associated with their performance in English. A descriptive survey method was adopted. The sample comprised 100 Class X students, equally divided into 50 boys and 50 girls, selected randomly from secondary schools in Tehsil Jalalabad West, Fazilka, Punjab. Emotional intelligence was measured through the Seven Fold Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Khera, Ahuja, and Kaur (2002), while academic achievement in English was assessed through marks obtained in the final Class X examination. Mean, standard deviation, t-test, and product-moment correlation were used for statistical analysis. The findings revealed a positive and significant correlation between academic achievement in English and emotional intelligence, indicating that emotionally intelligent students tend to perform better in English. Gender-wise comparison showed no statistically significant difference between boys and girls in English achievement or emotional intelligence, although girls obtained higher mean scores on both variables. The study highlights the need to integrate emotional intelligence development with English teaching to improve students' academic performance and social competence.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a life long process. Man becomes a man through education. Education makes a man a perfect person for the society. In the wider sense education is life and life is education. According to Rigveda, “Education is that which makes a man self reliant and self less.” Education is the mean to achieve the goal. Education is a process of promoting the harmonious development of a person capable of exercising such responsibilities in the society as her powers allow and directed towards the merger of the individual self with her universal self as the final end. During her studies a student passes through various stages of education i.e. primary, middle, secondary and higher. Secondary education is the backbone of entire educational system. Education after primary stage and prior to the university level is regarded as secondary education

Place of english

In these days english plays a key role in indian education system. Now, English is compulsory subject in our education. It should be taught on compulsory basis to all pupils as part of general education during the first ten years of schooling. English is an international language and its importance in education and student’s life cannot be denied.

Academic achievement

Academic achievement means the amount of knowledge gained by the students in different subjects of study. It is the status of a person's learning and his ability what he has learnt. It means the extend to which teaching and studying have resulted in mastery of the subject. It is the out come of general and specific learning experiences. It encourages the students to work hard and learn more. Also it helps the teacher to know weather their teaching methods are effective or not and helps them to bring improvements accordingly. Thus an academic achievement helps both the teachers and students to know where they stand.

Emotional intelligence

The term 'Emotional Intelligence' was coined by John Mayar and Peter Salovery and was popularized by Daniel Goleman in 1995. Emotional Intelligence, often measured as an emotional intelligence quotient describes an ability, capacity or skill to perceive, assess and manage the emotions of one's self, of others and of groups.

It is new concept and no one can yet say exactly how much of variability from person to person in life's it accounts for, but it can be powerful as I.Q. even high I.Q. is no guarantee of prosperity, prestige or happiness in life.

Need and significance of the study

Emotional intelligence has come to be regarded as a new measure of success in our professional and personal life. It focuses on personal qualities such as initiative, empathy, adaptability, persuasiveness, motivation and awareness. Academic achievement is the primary concern and most important goal of education. Academic achievement plays a very significant and vital role in the attainment of ideas of harmonious development of the pupil.

The present study has made an attempt to study of academic achievement in English in relation to emotional intelligence of Xth grade students. It is hoped that the study will contribute some highlights towards teaching of English. It will help the teacher to understand, whether the teaching methods are effective or not and help them in bringing improvement accordingly.

Statement of the problem

Academic Achievement in English in relation to Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School Students.

Objectives of the study

- To study the relationship between academic achievement in English and

- emotional intelligence of secondary school students.
- To compare academic achievement in English of boys and girls of secondary school students.
 - To compare emotional intelligence of boys and girls of secondary school students.

Hypotheses of the study

- There was no significant relationship between academic achievement in English and emotional intelligence of secondary school students.
- There was no significant difference between academic achievement in English of boys and girls of secondary school students.
- There was no significant difference between emotional intelligence of boys and girls of secondary school students.

Delimitations of the study

- The study was delimited to sample of 100 students.
- Students studying in Tehsil Jalalabad (west) was involved.
- Students of secondary school was taken.

Method of the study

The descriptive survey method was employed.

Sample of the study

A sample of 100 students (50 boys & 50 girls) of secondary school students was selected randomly for present study.

Tools to be used

- Seven fold emotional intelligence scale (SFEIS) is standardized and cross validated by Khera, V., Ahuja, P and Kaur, S. (2002).
- Marks obtained by students in their final examination of the Xth class.

Statistical techniques

- Mean, SD. And t-test was employed to see the significant difference between the groups.
- Product Moment Correlation was employed to see the significant relationship between Variables.

Analysis And Interpretation

This chapter deals with the analysis and interpretation of results. The collected data has been logically arranged and subjected to various statistical techniques for the purpose of analysis, interpretation and testing of hypotheses.

Hypotheses -1

There is no significant relationship between academic achievement in English and emotional intelligence of secondary school students.

Table 4.1

Coefficient of correlation between academic achievement in english and emotional intelligence of secondary school students

Variable	N	df	Coefficient of correlation	Level of Significance
Academic Achievement	100	198	0.19	Significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level
Emotional Intelligence	100			

Table 4.1 shows that the coefficient of correlation between academic achievement in English and emotional intelligence of secondary school students is 0.19 which is positive

and significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level. The table value at 0.05 level is .138 and at 0.01 level is .181. This indicates that academic achievement in english and emotional intelligence of secondary school students are positively and significantly correlated. So, hypotheses 1 there is no significant relationship between academic achievement in English and emotional intelligence of secondary school students has been rejected.

Hypotheses-2

There is no significant difference between academic achievement in english of boys and girls of secondary school students.

Table 4.2

Comparison of academic achievement in English of boys and girls

S.No.	Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD.	Df	SED	t-ratio	Level of Significance
1	Academic Achievement	Boys	50	120.15	11.44	48	2.48	1.67	Not significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level
2		Girls	50	124.30	13.36				

Table 4.2 reveals that Mean and SD for boys are 120.15 and 11.44. Mean and SD for girls are 124.30 and 13.36. The calculated t- value is 1.67 which is not significant at 0.01 & 0.05 level of significance. The table value at 0.05 level is 1.96 and at 0.01 level is 2.58. It means that there is no significant difference in the academic achievement in english of boys and girls of secondary school students. Hence the hypotheses 2 that there is no significant difference between academic achievement in english of boys and girls of secondary school students has been accepted. The mean scores of girls are greater than

that of boys. It means that girls are more academically talented in English as compared to boys of secondary school students.

Hypotheses-3

There is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of boys and girls of secondary school students.

Table 4.3

Comparison of emotional intelligence of boys and girls

S.No.	Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD.	Df	SED	t-ratio	Level of Significance
1	Emotional Intelligence	Boys	50	175.30	9.64	48	1.75	1.62	Not significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level
2		Girls	50	178.15	7.75				

Table 4.3 reveals that Mean and SD for boys are 175.30 and 9.64. Mean and SD for girls are 178.15 and 7.75. The calculated t-value is 1.62 which is significant at 0.01 & 0.05 level of significance. The table value at 0.05 level is 1.96 and at 0.01 level is 2.58. It means that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of boys and girls of secondary school students. Hence the hypothesis 3 that there is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of boys and girls of secondary school students has been accepted. The mean scores of girls are greater than that of boys. It means that girls are more emotionally mature as compared to boys of secondary school students.

Findings of the study

1. Academic achievement in English and emotional intelligence of secondary school students are positively and significantly correlated.
2. Significant difference in the academic achievement in English of boys and girls of secondary school students. Girls are more academically talented in English than boys.
3. Significant difference in the emotional intelligence of boys and girls of secondary school students. Girls are more emotionally mature in English as compared to boys.

Educational implications

1. Emotional intelligence of English skills should be made imperative in the curriculum.
2. Parents and teachers provide better opportunities for boys to improve their academic achievement better in english.
3. Parents and teachers must help the children to teach the methods of proper development of social skills for better communication.

Suggestions for further research

- The study should be extended to the urban and rural students.
- The study should be conducted on large sample.
- The study should be conducted on many other variables.
- The study should be conducted on other districts.
- The study may be conducted on academic achievement in relation to some other variables.
- The study may be conducted on college or university students.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

AbiSamra, N. (2000). The relationship between emotional intelligent and academic achievement in eleventh graders. *Research in Education*, FED.661.

Ahuja. (2004). A study of academic achievement of adolescents in relation to parental involvement and aspirations. *Indian Educational Review*, 40(2),58-75.

Alam, M.M. (2009). The relationships between the emotional intelligence and job satisfaction. empirical findings from higher education institution in Malaysia. *Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 15(2), 124-139.

Bala,K.(2009).A study of Relationship emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence of

secondary school students. Unpublished M.Ed Dissertation, PU, CHD.

Bansi B., & Pathan, Y. (2004). Emotional intelligence of secondary teachers in relation genders and age. *Asian Journal of Psychology and Education*. 39(5-6), 18-21.

Binnet, A., & Simon, T. (1916). *The development of intelligence in children*, Baltimore; Williams & Wilkins.

Boyatzis, R.E., Goleman, D., Rhee, K. (2000). Clustering competence in emotional intelligence: Insights from the emotional competence inventory, In R. Bar-on and D.A. Parker, *Handbook of Emotional Intelligence*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

Boyd, M.A. (2005). *The emotional intelligence of teachers and students perceptions of their teachers behaviour in the classroom*. *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 66(3), 898-A.

Campbell, M.K. (2000). Exploring the relationship between emotional intelligence, intuition and responsible risk-taking in organizations. *Dissertation Abstracts International-B*, 61(12), 6750.

Cooper, R.K., & Sawaf, A. (1997). *Executive EQ: emotional intelligence in leadership and organizations*. New York: Grosset / Putnam.

Coover., & Murphy (2000). *The communicated self*. *Human Communication Research*, 26(1), 125-148.

Crow, L.D., & Crow, A. (1969). *Adolescent development and adjustment*, McGraw-Hill Book Company, United State.

Crow, L.D., & Crow, A. (1973). *Educational Psychology* (3rd Indian reprint), New Delhi; Eurasia Publishing House, 83.

Darsana, M. (2007). Relationship between emotional intelligence and certain achievement facilitating variables of higher secondary school students. *Edutracks*, 7 (4), 25-31.

Donaldson- Feilder, E.J., & Bond, F.W. (2004). The relative importance of psychological acceptance and emotional intelligence to workplace well being. *British Journal of Guidance & Counselling*, 32 (2), 187-203.

Elizabeth, R. (2008). The relationship among life-long learning, emotional intelligence and life satisfaction. *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 68(7),2764-A.

Gautam,R.(2000).The Relationship between emotional intelligence and success in school for a sample of 8th grade students. *Dissertation Abstracts*, 62(5), 4312.

Ghareteph, A. (2015). Emotional intelligence as a predictor of self-efficacy among students with different levels of academic achievement at Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences. Retrieved on October16, 2016 from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>

Goleman,D.(1995).Emotional Intelligence. NewYork: Bantam Books.

Halawah, I.(2006).The effects of motivation,family environment and student characteristics on academic achievement. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*. 25.

Hans, A. (2013). A Study on Emotional Intelligence among Teachers: A Case study of Private Educational Institutions in Muscat. Retrieved on September 20, 2016 from www.ijaiem.org/volume2issue7/IJAIEM-2013-07-25-090.pdf

Heastie., &Samuel,R.(2001).Relationship and difference on self regulated learning, parental involvement, homework and academic achievement among high school students in rural West Virginia. *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 62(5), 4312.

Jaeger, A.J. (2001). Job competencies and the curriculum, an Enquiry into Emotional Intelligence in Graduate Professional Education. Manusript Submitted for ASHE Conference.

Kalia , A., &Sahoo, S. (2010). A study of general well being in relation to gender, birth orderand academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Studies*, 8(2), 1-5.

Katyal,S.,&Awarthi.E(2009).“Gender differences in emotional intelligence among adolescents of CHD”. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 17,153-155.

Kumari,A.(2013).Self concept and academic achievement at the higher secondary students. *Journal of Sociological Research*,4(2).

Kumari,V.R.S(2015).Achievement Motivation, Study Habits and Academic

Achievement of Students at the Secondary Level. Retrieved on September 20, 2016 from

https://www.ermt.net/docs/papers/Volume_4/10_October2015/V4N10-122.pdf

Labhana,C.P.(2015).Self concept and emotional intelligence: A comparative study of arts and science college students. The International Journal of Indian Psychology, 2(2).

Ladson,B.G.(1999).Can't any body teach children? The promise of culturally relevant teaching,

Teaching today for tomorrow.1, 2.

Levy, D.M.(1942).Maternal and Protection, New York, Columbia University Press.

Mahajan, M. (2011). "Academic achievement in relation to emotional intelligence and Spiritual intelligence" Educational Tracks, (9), 32-36.

Mangal,S.K.(2004). Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory. Agra: National Psychological Corporation.

Manger.,& Eikeland(2006).The effect of mathematics self-concept on girls' and boys' mathematical achievement. School Psychology International, 19(1), 5-18.

Mayer, J.D., & Salovey, P. (1990). Emotional intelligence. imagination, cognition and personality, 9(3), 185-211.

Mayer, J.D., Salovey, P., Goldman, S.L., Turvey, C., & Palfai, T.P. (2000). Emotional attention, clarity and repair exploring emotional intelligence using the trait Meta-Mood scale.

McDougall,W.G.(1949).An outline of psychology(13thed).London,Methuen.

Murensky, C.L. (2000). The relationship between emotional intelligence, personality, critical thinking ability and organizational leadership performance at upper levels of management. Dissertation Abstracts International-B 61(02), 1121.

Netto, T.Y. (2004). Influence of home environment and achievement of fishermen students at higher secondary level. Unpublished M. Ed Thesis, Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam.

Palmer, B.W., Burgess, Z., & Stough, C. (2001). Emotional intelligence and effective leadership. *Leadership and Organizational Development Journal*, 25, 5-10

Pennebaker, J.W. (Ed.), *Emotional disclosure and health*. Washington, D.C.: American Psychological Association.

Punithavathi, P. (2011). Creativity, self-concept and academic achievement among students at the secondary level, M.Ed. Thesis, Tamilnadu Teachers Education University, Chennai.

Rana, R.A., & Iqbal, Z.F. (2005). Effect of Students' Self-Concept and Gender on Academic Achievement in Science. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 27(2), 19-36.

Sharma, N. (2011). A study of emotional intelligence of school students in relation to mental health.

Un published dissertation in M.Phil Education. Patiala: Punjabi University

Sharma, M., & Tahira K. (2011). Family variables as predictors of students achievement in science. *Journal of Community Guidance & Research*, 28, (1), 28-36.

Shiple, N.L. (2014.) The effects of emotional intelligence, age, work experience, and academic performance. Retrieved on September 20, 2016 from www.aabri.com/manuscripts/10535.pdf

Singh, D. (2003). *Emotional Intelligence at Work: A Professional Guide*. New Delhi: Response Books.

Sinha, A.K., & Jain, A.K. (2004). Emotional intelligence imperative for the organizationally relevant outcomes. *Psychological Studies*, 49(2&3), 18-26.

Spinoza, B. (1677). *Ethics*. Incurley (Eds.), *The collected works of Spinoza*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.

Stein, S.J., & Book, H.E. (2000). The EQ Edge, New Delhi: Mc Millan India. Stoddard,G.D.(1943).The meaning of intelligence, NewYork:Macmillian,4.

Thorndike,E.L.(1914).Educational Psychology (Briefercourse), New York: Columbia university.

VanRooy,D.L.,&Viswesvaran,C.(2004).Emotional intelligence: A metaanalytic investigation of predictive validity and nomological.net. Journal of Vocational Behavior, 65, 71-95.

Wechesler,D.(1944).The measurement of adult intelligence(3rded.),New York:Williams&Wilkins.

Wood worth, R.S(1945).Psychology,London:Methuen,410.